

Participant supplementary booklet

Group activity: applying to scientific conferences

Led by: Kes Maio (JIC)

This workshop will use peer-assisted methods to explore two key steps in the scientific conference application process: writing a strong abstract and preparing a competitive travel grant application. A well-written abstract is vital to secure a place at the conference, and to inform colleagues in the field what your interests are and your current research area. This could allow for potential collaborators to seek you out during the course of, or sometimes even before, the conference. This workshop will cover what makes an abstract clear, concise, and compelling, and use peer feedback to review examples.

Travel grants provide crucial financial support while also adding recognition and prestige to your CV and future applications. This workshop will explore how to tailor applications to specific awards, highlight your research and background effectively, and ensure your application meets eligibility criteria. Practical exercises and collaborative feedback will offer strategies to optimise both abstracts and grant applications, boosting chances of success at any potential future conference.

How to write a successful abstract:

It is important to remember 4S's when preparing an abstract for a scientific conference. Firstly, it is key to keep abstracts **short**. Often there are word limits on abstracts, but generally they should be kept to under 150 words. They must also be **simple**, highlighting the research you do in as few as two sentences. Ideally, this should be accessible so that people who are not in your field can also understand the basic concepts underlying your research. Despite this, it is also key to make sure you are also **specific**, highlighting what makes your work unique and **significant**. Abstracts should not be so specific that you need to include citations or references. Specific scientific jargon can be useful where appropriate but you may be alienating potential inter-disciplinary collaborators if this is too frequent.

Checklist:

- What is the rationale or context underlying your research question?
- Have you defined your research question and your hypotheses?
- What methods and techniques are you employing to answer your research question?
- Have you summarised your most important results briefly?
- What is the significance of your work?

Writing travel grant applications

Travel grants provide a competitive means of securing funding to attend conferences in costly locations, while also showcasing your value as a researcher within the community. Often travel grants are secured from the conference itself, from non-profit societies associated with your area of research or from award schemes.

Some examples of places to apply include: Genetics Society, The Company of Biologists, Royal Society, CGIAR, Wellcome Trust, Schlumberger Foundation, American Society for Horticultural Science, West African Research Association (WARA), Africa Health Research Institute (AHRI), Southeast Asian Regional Centre for Graduate Study and Research in Agriculture (SEARCA), African Union Kwame Nkrumah Scientific Awards, African Women in Agricultural Research and Development (AWARD).

It is important to note that some travel grants stipulate that you have not applied to other travel grants to be awarded with their award. Before starting your application, you will often need to have **submitted your abstract** and been **accepted to attend** the conference. Check the requirements of the travel grant also and make sure you **fit the requirements**, e.g. are you an early career researcher? A woman in STEM

(Science/Technology/Engineering/Mathematics)? A resident or born in the country the grant is tailored towards? Often you and/or your supervisor will need to be a **member of the society** (which may also require payment) in order to apply for a society grant. These will be specific to the funding body so remember to check!

It is key to remember - throughout your application - what conferences are for. Firstly, they provide a space for academics to share new and state-of-the-art research with the research community. Secondly, but equally as importantly, they provide a space for scientists to connect with each other, brainstorm new ideas, and form new collaborations. Highlight your interest in both of these functions of conferences by following the 'CO-LINC' checklist below and remember to tailor your application to the funding body AND the conference you are applying for funding to travel to.

Remember to CO-LINC:

- Contribute** - what is your research question? How does it add/apply to the themes of the conference?
- Optimise** - how do you plan to optimise your stay in the place you are travelling to? How will this help your career development?
- Learn** - are there specific people you would like to see present?
- Interests** - how is this conference appropriate and appeals to your interests? Ties into what you could learn
- Network** - who is attending/ what field is highlighted which may include attendees you would like to expand your network with?
- Collaborate** - is anyone specific attending who you would like to meet/ how might this help with future collaborations/ interdisciplinary work?

Finally, double check everything yourself and get someone to read over this for you. They will hopefully spot any spelling or grammar errors and let you know if there's something you've forgotten to include. They may even know someone attending who it would be important for you to meet for your work. This extra justification could add to the strength of your application. Good luck!

Exercises

Day 1

During the workshop, read through the provided travel grant in your groups and answer the following questions:

What does the travel grant do well?

What could be improved?

Would you approve this travel grant?

Day 2

You can write your travel grant either on your laptops or using the space provided. Remember to CO-LINC.

This exercise is to hone your travel grant. You will give feedback on your peer's travel grant and vice-versa. It is important to provide constructive changes throughout this exercise and focus on the writing.

Swap your travel grant with person 1. Person 1 will share:

Two good things about your travel grant:

Two things to improve about your travel grant:

Swap your travel grant with person 2. Person 2 will share:

Two good things about your travel grant:

Two things to improve about your travel grant:

Swap your travel grant with person 3. Person 3 will share:

Two good things about your travel grant:

Two things to improve about your travel grant:

Group Activity: communicating science to different audiences

Led by: **Matthew Shackleton-Chavez (University of East Anglia)**

In this session we shall learn and practice how to communicate science to different scientific and non-scientific audiences. This is an important skill because as scientists it is our responsibility to ensure our work is known and understood, to ensure we maintain trust in science, funding for future research, and highlight the importance of our work for the future of humanity. We will first overview what kind of audiences we may encounter in our careers, and then role play scenarios to explain different scientific concepts to different audiences, such as politicians, school children, and business investors.

How scientists should approach specific groups of people (Note taking):

Politician

Business Leader/Investor

Potential Employer - Academic

Potential Employer - Industry

Young Child (under 10 years old)

Young Adult (teenager)

Working Age Adult

Retired Adult

Biology Undergraduate

Different Scientist (e.g Physicist)

School Teacher

Parent/Guardian/Carer

Descriptions of what specific people look for in scientists (group activity):

Politician:

- Clarity and simplified aims
- Translational outcomes specified
- Prestige for themselves
- Return on investment

Business leader / investor:

- Short elevator pitch
- Clear product/translational pathway specified
- Idea of how much this will cost to invest in
- Timeline specified for the work

Potential employer - academic:

- Publications
- Techniques and skills you are proficient in
- Someone they can work with
- How you could see your role in their research

Potential employer - industry:

- Experience and skills clearly detailed
- Translational skills you possess
- Someone they can work with

Young child (under 10 years old):

- Simplified explanations
- Clear aims of your research
- Clear rationale and basis
- Metaphors and cool examples
- Hands on, tangible experience

Young adult (teenager):

- Not as simplified explanations
- Examples of experiences and cool stories
- Cool examples and videos
- Hands on, tangible experience

Working age adult:

- Explanations that are understandable with metaphors
- Clear explanation of the aims and rationale
- Translational applications

Retired adult:

- Explanations that are understandable with metaphors
- Clear explanation of the aims and rationale
- Translational applications

Undergraduate:

- Inspiration
- Perspective on what the research life is like
- Advice, for careers

Different scientist (e.g Physicist):

- To make a friend
- Technical and transferable skills
- Interdisciplinary collaboration

School teacher:

- The scientists abilities to explain the ideas simply
- Wow factor, something cool, inspiring for students
- Summaries of state of the art research

Parent / guardian / carer:

- Enjoying their research
- Simplified explanations that they could tell others
- Job security
- Work life balance

Descriptions of Scientific Scenarios (For Group Activity):

Scenario 1: Explaining the function and purpose of a PCR

You work in a wheat lab as a research associate, you commonly clone to build plasmids and conduct PCR's on a regular basis. You have been asked to explain how and why we do PCR's in our molecular work.

Scenario 2: Describing the work of your lab

You work in a wheat lab which is using CRISPR to generate and trial novel mutant lines to increase crop yield. Your lab consists of 5 people, a professor, a postdoc who works on computational work, a research technician who works in the greenhouses, a masters student who is helping to generate novel mutant lines, and you - a PhD student who mostly does molecular work. Explain the function and purpose of each person in this lab.

Scenario 3: A recent discovery you have made

You work in a cutting-edge wheat lab and you have recently tested a novel promoter to produce Cas9 via a genomically integrated transgene, as well as an exogenously expressing plasmid. Your novel promoter has been functional and worked to produce CRISPR-Cas9 knockouts. Please explain this novel work and discovery you have made.

Scenario 4: You have made a novel invention that could be a product

In collaboration with labs in 3 different countries you have co-invented, via CRISPR-Cas9 genome edits, a miraculous strain of wheat which requires 40% less water per cubic metre of soil than any previously established strain. Your role in this was to design the plasmids used for gene editing. Your strain has not been tested over more than 3 generations and is patent pending in all 3 host countries. Please explain how this could be of potential benefit to the industry, and why people should trust this novel product.

Scenario 5: Your experiments haven't worked in 18 months

You work as a postdoc in an established lab, however your lab work has not worked or generated usable data for 18 months. Despite this, there is the potential for important breakthroughs if it works. Please explain your situation.

Scenario 6: What does a scientist do?

For this scenario, please describe what you do (the student reading this) in your normal role as a researcher/student.

Construct design and assembly

Led by: Matthew Shackleton-Chavez (University of East Anglia)

A fundamental component of molecular biology and genome editing is the assembly and use of 'constructs', by which we mean engineered plasmids (rings of dsDNA). Constructs are modified to encode specific functions we would like to use for experimental purposes. In this lecture, we will cover the fundamentals of what a plasmid is, examples of the components used in existing plasmids, and the design of a plasmid we will assemble together in the second week of the course.

This will be followed by an in-depth explanation of how we build plasmids. We will focus on the Golden Gate method, which combines restriction digestion and ligation into a one-pot reaction, but will also touch on the Gibson assembly method. This session will also contain an interactive component, in which we will visually explore how to assemble constructs using overhangs or 'sticky ends' with complementary sequences. By the end of the session we hope to have given you an overview of how constructs are assembled and the key components they encode - including those relating to CRISPR-Cas9 genome editing.

Acronym guide:

CRISPR-Cas9: Clustered Regularly Interspaced Short Palindromic Repeats-Cas9

Cas9: CRISPR-Associated Protein 9 (an endonuclease)

gRNA: guide Ribonucleic Acid

sgRNA: single guide Ribonucleic Acid (name of the synthetic combination of a gRNA recognition site + the fused gRNA core which binds to the Cas9 protein)

RNP: Ribonucleoprotein complex (gRNA-Cas9 combined is an example of an RNP)

DSB: Double Stranded Break (of DNA)

InDel: Insertion and/or Deletion on a DNA sequence

HDR: Homology Directed Repair (DNA repair using a donor template)

NHEJ: Non-Homologous End Joining (DNA repair without a donor template)

PAM: Protospacer Adjacent Motif (a 3-base DNA sequence adjacent to Cas9 cut sites, sequence: NGG)

PCR: Polymerase Chain Reaction

qPCR: quantitative Polymerase Chain Reaction

GG: Golden Gate (plasmid assembly method)

Quick molecular biology and gene editing concepts:

Homology directed repair (HDR) and non-homologous end joining (NHEJ): HDR is when a DNA break is repaired by copying the same region on the homologous chromosome. NHEJ is when a DNA break is repaired without a DNA template, resulting in sequence variants.

Plasmid: A ring of double-stranded DNA, they exist in nature as miniature genomes and artificial ones are used in molecular biology as expression vectors.

RNA polymerase II promoter: An encoded DNA region which is bound by a Pol II protein to produce an mRNA of the downstream encoded gene. Used to express genes such as GFP and Cas9.

RNA polymerase III promoter: An encoded DNA region which is bound by a Pol III protein to produce a short non-coding RNA - such as a gRNA.

Molecular cloning: A term used for the preparation of chosen DNA fragments to be used for plasmid assembly. We call this 'cloning' because it involves isolating a specific DNA sequence and making (hopefully) identical copies of it.

Endonuclease: A term for a molecule (protein or RNA) which has the ability to cause breaks in nucleotide chains.

Type II and type IIS restriction enzymes: Type II enzymes cut at the DNA recognition site, whereas type IIS cut at a site adjacent to the recognition site. The digestion-ligation assembly method uses type II enzymes, whereas Golden Gate assembly uses type IIS.

Golden Gate recognition sites: A method for fragment preparation and plasmid assembly, which uses type IIS restriction enzymes to cleave DNA and cause sticky overhangs in regions near the recognition site - the result being that one can perform a "scarless" plasmid assembly. An example of a Type IIS Restriction Enzymes is BsaI, which, depending on the orientation of the recognition site, can cut at the sites shown below:

Figure 1. BsaI enzyme recognition sites and where they cut depending on the orientation of the DNA.

Digestion-ligation recognition sites overview:

A method in which a type II restriction enzyme is used to cleave DNA at a specified site to create 'overhangs' or 'sticky ends' which can then be used for plasmid assembly. This method often results in 'scars' of extra DNA in the sequence. In this method, DNA fragments are first amplified with overhangs which encode for the enzyme recognition site to build the sequence on the ends of the fragments. The fragments are then 'digested' with the chosen enzyme to expose sticky ends which can anneal with other fragments. These fragments are joined together, or 'ligated', with a DNA ligase.

An example of a restriction enzyme cut site is FseI (pictured below). This displays how the cut site is at the same location as the enzyme recognition sequence (unlike a type IIS enzyme).

Figure 2. FseI cut site displaying the sticky overhangs generated, which are then used to anneal to another FseI sticky overhang.

Gibson assembly overview:

A method for plasmid assembly in which large primers (oligonucleotides) are used which have complementary recognition to two separate DNA fragments, and is used to bring together fragments in a scarless manner. First, fragments are amplified with the Gibson primers, which have the complementary half and the overhanging segment - which are then used for plasmid assembly as the overhang binds to the complementary fragment and fuses the fragments together.

Figure 3. An image displaying an insert in a Gibson assembly, with the primer orientations and overhangs which cover regions on both fragments.

Analysing Sanger sequencing data with Benchling

Led by: **Matthew Shackleton-Chavez (University of East Anglia)**

Sanger sequencing is a popular method for analysing the sequence and/or variants of a short region of DNA/RNA. In this session we shall overview the process of why we use Sanger sequencing, and how to prepare samples for analysis. Furthermore we will detail how the sequencing works on the molecular level, followed by a tutorial on Benchling in which we will learn how to align and interpret the sequence data files produced, including the chromatograms and basepair confidence scores. By the end of this session we should be able to understand the function of Sanger sequencing, as well as how to understand and analyze the sequence results generated.

Key Concepts for Sanger Sequencing Results Analysis:

Phred Score:

Table 1. Phred score displaying how the quality score correlates to the probability the consensus base call is correct.

Phred quality score	Probability of incorrect base call	Base call accuracy
10	1 in 10	90%
20	1 in 100	99%
30	1 in 1000	99.9%
40	1 in 10,000	99.99%
50	1 in 100,000	99.999%
60	1 in 1,000,000	99.9999%

Chromatograms:

Chromatograms are visual displays which show the confidence of each base call with coloured lines - each colour represents a base identity. In high-confidence regions, each locus will have a predominant peak, whereas there will be multiple peaks at a given locus if the base's identity is less certain. Figure 1 below displays a short amplicon sequenced using Sanger sequencing. This amplicon contains very low confidence base calls for the first quarter or so of the sequence, followed by much higher confidence calls for most of the remainder.

Figure 1. A short fragment sequenced by Sanger, displaying a range of base confidence calls.

Group Activity: scientific posters and presentations

Led by: **Matthew Shackleton-Chavez (University of East Anglia)**

This session focuses on two activities for learning and discussing scientific posters and presentations. This session will allow you to examine and critique examples of posters and presentations, to avoid common mistakes and create better content for your future careers. The first segment is on posters in which we shall teach good poster design, followed by small group activities in which you will examine and rate a selection of pre-prepared posters based on the poster's merits, followed by open floor discussion between groups for which the best and worst attributes will be discussed. The second segment shall first introduce the concepts of good presentation design and delivery, followed by small group activities examining example poster slides, followed by open floor discussion.

Checklist for posters:

- Is the title clear and concise?
- Are the author(s) names clearly visible?
- Are the host institution(s) and funders logo's/acknowledgements present?
- Is the key narrative of the poster clear in its introduction, aims, results and conclusion?
- Are the subsections clearly labelled with sub titles?
- Is the written text concise and to the point?
- Is the text of a readable size?
- Are the figures (including legends!) of a clear and readable size?
- Are there any large empty spaces that should be filled?
- Is the colour contrast between text and background(s) readable?
- Is the key information readable from 3 meters away?

Checklist for presentations:

- Is there too much text on the slides?
- Have you used the "Assertion-Evidence" Method?
- Is the introduction clear and concise?
- Are the aims and purpose of the presentation clear?
- Are the methods clear and understood?
- Are the results readable and clearly displayed?
- Is the conclusion clear?
- Do all figures have legends? Do they have keys if required?
- Do all tables have column/row headings with units? Is a legend required?
- Is legend text large enough to be visible at the back of the room?
- Is the colour contrast between text and background readable?
- Does the presentation over-run its allotted time? If so it must be trimmed down.
- Are all contributors acknowledged?
- Are your supervisors, institution(s), and funders acknowledged?

Example Poster Layouts:

What To Look For That These Layouts Do Well:

- Clear separation of segments with subtitles and/or boxes
- Clear colours and no saturation
- Clear title and location
- Your name and host institution are present
- Acknowledgements present
- Readable figure sizes
- No empty spaces however not overflowing with content

What to avoid that is not on layouts:

- Too much text
- Ensure your poster is understandable from 3 meters away
- Consistency in font and subtitle sizes - easier to follow
- Don't have too many figures! 3 or 4 is plenty!

Scientific Poster Template

Title (40 point type): Informative, short, mention of the study design and findings
 Add author names and information: the list and sequence of authors remains unchanged from the abstract to poster
 Include university or department names if needed (24 point type): the superscript number denotes each author's affiliation

Introduction

- Introduction should be 1-3 bullet points on relevant background information & rationale
- Font size 14 point type

Objectives

- Bulleted list of 2-3 research questions
- Font size 14 point type

Methods

- Basic information about:
 - Study design and duration
 - Inclusion and exclusion criteria
 - Drug regimens
 - Sample size
 - Patient population
 - Statistical methodology
 - Primary & secondary variables
 - Tolerability measures
 - NCT number, if applicable
- Font size 14 point type

	Heading	Heading	Heading
Item	800	790	8001
Item	356	854	290
Item	228	134	218
Item	994	879	979
Item	334	326	301
Item	190	137	356

Results

- Patient numbers (flow chart)
- Patient demographics (table)
- Findings presented in the form of table/figures
- Highlights of key findings; bulleted text relating findings back to initial aim and hypothesis
- Table
 - Place it shortly after textual reference
 - Columns and rows should be evenly spaced
 - Foot notes to the symbols used should appear below table body
- Font size 14 point type

Figure 1: Overview of study methodology

- Creating a protocol
- Participating in trials on-line journals and IT patient organizations
- Start sample size 1,000
- Start feedback loop September 2007 - February 2008
- Survey conducted online
- Start data mining

Conclusions

- Summary of findings (2-3 sentences in plain English)
- Implications for research
- Directions for future research
- Study strengths and limitations
- Font size 20 point type

References

- This is dummy text used for illustrative purpose.

Disclosures

- This is dummy text used for illustrative purpose.

Acknowledgements

- This is dummy text used for illustrative purpose.

Congress details Sponsorship details

Notes

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